

**ASSESSMENT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT IN KHARALWADI
SLUM OF PIMPRI CHINCHWAD MUNICIPAL CORPORATION NEAR
PUNE IN MAHARASHTRA, INDIA.**

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Abstract:

Slums as a part of the urban settlement which can always affect the urban environment of nearby location. Most of the people of slum area work on any occupational system of nearby localities. They may work as driver, watchmen, wage labour, garbage collector, hotel waiter, and so on many think the working population include child labour. Because of some reasons it is therefore one of the basic problem of slum in any urban areas.

The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data including the field survey, secondary data from Pimpri Chinchwad Municipal Corporation and also computer based technique. This paper examines the assessment of socio-economic environment like, Caste status, occupational status, educational status, age group wise population distribution and home appliances in Kharalwadi slum.

Key Words: *Field work, area measurement, assessment of social environment and assessment of economical environment.*

1. Introduction:

Socio-economic (also known as social economic) is the social science that studies how economic activity affects and is shaped by social processes. In general it analyzes how societies progress, stagnate, or regress because of their local or regional economy, or the global economy. In many cases, socioeconomics focus on the social impact of some sort of economic change. Such changes might include a population status, occupation and income etc. Such social effects can be wide-ranging in size,

anywhere from local effects on a small community to changes to an entire society. The goal of socioeconomic study is generally to bring about socioeconomic development, usually by improvements in metrics such as GDP, life expectancy, literacy, levels of employment, etc

2. Aims & objectives of study:

1. To study the social assessment like, cast and education of Kharalwadi slum area.
2. To study economic assessment like, occupational status and home appliances of slum in Kharalwadi slum area.

3. Methodology:

3.1 Selection of site:

One slum region is selected for study in Pimpri-Chinchwad Municipal Area. Selection of slum pockets with base of stratified random sampling method were performed in the ratio of 1:03 and Kharalwadi Slum in Pimpri-Chinchwad is selected. This slum is situated near Pune-Mumbai highway. Slum is having variation in social and economic structure.

3.2 Data collection:

Data collection has done with the help of the interviews, observation, photos, Google images and field survey. Questionnaires has prepared for getting information of social and economic status. However spatial analysis of study area has been done on Google image using Arc GIS in order to calculate area and related features. This paper will be mostly focus on social and economic status of study area.

3.3 The location of study area:

The location of Kharalwadi in Pimpri-Chinchwad is situated beside the PCMC head building, 612 m above sea level. Kharalwadi is located on 18°32'30.21"N latitude and 73° 52'0.58" E longitude. Kharalwadi slum in Pimpri-Chinchwad is situated in left side of PCMC office.

4 Assessment of socio-economic environment in study area:

4.1 Age Group wise Population in study area:

Age group wise population analysis also plays an important role in knowing basic structure of society. According to the study there are major 72.54% of population is in between 15-60 age group and 25.98% of population is below 15 age. And 1.47% of population is above 60. It is shown in following table.

Table no.1: Age-wise population Status

Age Group	Population	Percentage
Below 15	53	25.98%
15-60	148	72.54%
Above 60	3	1.47%
Total	204	99.99%

Figure no.1: Age Group Population Status

4.2 Cast wise status of study area:

It is also important to know which communities are living in slum areas and can analyze their standard of living. According to study in Kharalwadi slum area more population is of S.C. community which is 66%, followed by Open (26%), N.T. (8%).

Table no.2: Cast wise Status

Cast	No. of Family	Percentage
Open	13	26%
N.T.	4	8%
S.C.	33	66%
Total	50	100%

Figure no.2: Cast Status

4.3 Educational status of study area:

Educational status of any area impacts on literacy and overall development of that area. In the slum of Kharalwadi there is 28% peoples are Illiterate. And remaining having primary and secondary education and only few are having their graduation and post graduation which can be shown in the following table and chart.

Table no.3: Educational Status

Education Type	No. of Peoples	Percentage
Illiterate	58	28%
Primary	54	26.47%
Secondary	62	30.39%
Higher Secondary	19	9.31%
Gradation	7	3.43%
Post Graduation	4	1.96%
Total	204	100

Figure no.3: Educational Status

4.4 Occupational status of study area:

In the slum area of Kharalwadi, it is also important to study occupation of local people and local economy. This helps to identify poverty of people and their standard of living. In the study area there are 53 wage labors, 21 peoples doing their private services and nearly 112 people are non-worker out of **204** as total population.

Table no.4: Occupational Status

Occupation	No. of People	Percentage
Wage Labour	53	25.98
Service	21	10.29
Non-Worker	112	54.9
Business	18	8.82
Total	204	99.99

Figure no.4: Occupational Structure

4.5 Availability of home appliances in Study area:

Different day to day facility survey has been done in the study area in order to find the standard of living in slum area. It can be observed there is sufficient amount of facilities in the slum area. It is shown in following table.

Table no.5: Available Facility Status

Facility	No. of family	Percentage (%)
Fan	46	92
Mobile	50	100
T.V.	48	96
Motorcycle	23	46
Fridge	43	86
Gas	41	82
Cooler	7	14
Total no. of Family: 50		

Figure no.4: Available Facilities

5. Conclusion:

In the study area of Kharalwadi slum in Pimpri-Chinchwad, It can be concluded that economic structure of backward class is low. Peoples living in this slum has low standard of living but having good amount of facilities & amenities. So there should be proper maintenance & town planning in the slum area.

6. Bibliography

Books:

- L.N.P. Mohanty and Swati Mohanty (2005) "Slums in India" APH Publishing Corporation. ISBN 817648-892-5.
- Henna Tabassum (2011) "Slums in India" ABD Publishers, ISBN 978-81-8376-333-2.
- Ratna N Rao (1990) "Social Organisation in an Indian Slum" Mittal Publications, ISBN 81-7009-186-2.
- Suhas Kulkarni (2010) "Ardhi Mumbai" Samkalin Prakashan.
- C.N. Ray (2003) "Liberalisation and urban social services- Health and Education" Rawat Publication, ISBN 81-7033-762-3.

Research Articles and Reports

- M.S. Deshmukh (2013) "Condition of slum population of major sub-urban wards of Mumbai in Maharashtra" Voice of research, Vol.2 Issue 2, ISSN No. 2277-7733.
- National Sample Survey Organisation (2004) "Housing Condition In India."
- Upinder Sawhney (2013) " Slum population in India: Extent and policy response." International Journal of research in Business and Social Science IJRBS Vol.2 ISSN: 2147-4478.